

PRINCIPLES AND PROBLEMS OF STUDYING LEXICAL DOUBLETS IN MODERN LINGUISTICS

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the functional semantic study of lexical doublets of English language. Moreover, the article considers the etymology of doublets which were borrowed from different languages, such as French, Latin and others and reveals comparison of English with other languages that has a great influence on the developmental process of English language, functional semantics of English doublets comparing with other languages by representing examples as well. In addition, the article gives an overview of the lexical-semantic features of doublets that borrowed from other languages and their etymology according to their origin..

Introduction

Lexical doublets represent one of the most extensive semantic categories. As a language rich in vocabulary items, English contains a great number of borrowed word forms. One result of this propensity to accept foreign words is cognates known as “doublets”. In etymology, two or more words in the same language are called doublets or etymological twins or twinlings when they have different phonological forms but the same etymological root. They typically occur in pairs but can also form larger groups of cognate word forms, which may be native and foreign cognates, repeated borrowings from a single language, or cognates from different languages.¹ For example: channel and canal, gaol and jail, beef and cow, chief and head. When the two words are used together in a phrase they are called coupled synonyms or binomial expressions.

Let's consider the etymological pair of words adamant and diamond, it is no coincidence that the basic meaning of adamant was diamond. The word diamond is a doublet of adamant, the two words having come ultimately from the same Greek source, adamantos. The present day adjective, meaning unyielding, inflexible, is usually in the phrase to be adamant, is 1st recorded in the 1930s. It was apparently an extended use of such earlier phrases as an adamant heart, meaning “a heart of stone” and adamant walls “stone walls”.²

¹ Karen Elizabeth Sesterhenn. (2016). An overview of the phenomenon of doublets in English. University of Georgia.

² Sol Steinmetz. (2008). Semantic Antics. Random House.

The word journal appeared in English in the 16th century and this word derived from French origin that is substantiated adjective *jurnal*. If we analyze the word *jurnal* or *jornal*, that comes from Latin origin *diurnalis* which means “daytime”. In modern English the word *journal* is a noun and means magazine, newspaper. The historical community of many etymological doublets may not be felt as present. Such doublets far diverged in form and meaning, and their comparison is carried out only when studying the language in historical terms. In practical terms, such words are not difficult, because they do not come together in the modern consciousness, either structurally or semantically.³ Doublets are often borrowed from related languages, and not particularly modest. So, for instance, the names of some meats (food) came from German into English, and the names of the corresponding animals came from some other Romance language.

As many researchers stated that if a doublet suddenly has another “relative”, then these are no longer twins, but triplets. An interesting example of such a constellation is a welcome from the heart – hearty welcome, sincere welcome. The common root is the ancient Indo-European word *ker*, from which Latin *cor*, Italian *cuore*, French *Coeur*, Spanish *Corazon*, German *herz* and English *heart* originate.⁴ Melinkoff also points out that many doublets and triplets combine words of Old English, Latin and Norman French origin. For example, *mind* (OE) – *memory* (L), *final* (F) – *conclusive* (L), *fit* (OE) – *proper* (F), *peace* (F) – *quiet* (L). These expressions are mostly centuries old, and some date from a time when it was advisable to use words of various origins either to increase intelligibility for people from different language backgrounds, or more probably it was intended to encompass previous legal usage or legal documents from both early English and Norman French.⁵

To sum up, we can say that the historical community of many etymological doublets may not be felt at present. Such doublets far diverged in form and meaning, and their comparison is carried out only when studying the language in historical terms. In practically they cannot be complex because they do not come together in present awareness.

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³ O. Yakubovich. (2020). Etymological and pro-etymological doublets in English. *International scientific journal*.

⁴ O. Yakubovich. (2020). Etymological and pro-etymological doublets in English. *International scientific journal*.

⁵ J. Gibbon. (2003). *Forensic Linguistics: An introduction to language in the Justice System*, Blackwell.